
LEADERSHIP STYLE: A DETERMINANT OF THE PERFORMANCE OF EMPLOYEE'S OF FEDERAL COLLEGE OF EDUCATION, OBUDU, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study evaluated leadership style: a determinant of the performance of employee's of federal college of education, Obudu, Nigeria. The researchers adopted descriptive research design. A population of 1184 was drawn from the personnels of the institution. To arrive at the sample size of 404, the researcher used Taro Yamane sample size determination, the data collected was analyzed with the aid of Statistical package for Social Science (SPSS)version 27.0. Findings indicated that transformational leadership style had a positive and significant relationship with employee performance of FCE, Obudu, the findings further revealed that participative leadership style positively and significantly affect the performance of employee in FCE Obudu. The study concluded that when the right leadership style is been implemented at the right time it enhances the performance of employee. Based on the findings the researcher recommended that Management should set up policy that will embrace transformational kind of leadership as the study has proven it to be very important in boosting the performance of the organization. Furthermore, the study recommended that Leaders should create opportunities for employees to contribute ideas and opinions during planning and problem-solving processes. This enhances employees' sense of ownership, responsibility, and commitment, which in turn improves performance and job satisfaction.

Keywords:

Leadership, Employee, Performance, Transformational, Participative, Organization.

Introduction

Leadership is a vital aspect of our day-to-day life, be its at the organizational level, religious level, schools and government. For any organization to get it right in the present days, the organization make have a leader that is proactive and act decisively in the running the organization activities

Past studies shows that bad leadership has led to the failure of many organization. Followership is a prerequisite for leadership; followership can be discouraged or encouraged by leadership. Particularly in an organization, the followers' total performance is determined by the leadership style. To put it another way, an organization's employees' performance can be positively enhanced by a good leadership style. According to research by Bronwell (2020), a key source of job discontent among employees is the organization's weak leadership.

Shahzadi et al. (2021) define employee performance as the quality and volume of output, attendance at work, helpfulness and accommodation, and timeliness of output. In order to accomplish goals and objectives, this relates to what an employee does and does not do while carrying out his daily responsibilities inside the company. It is the real contributions that employee makes to the achievement of the organization's goals and objectives. Nonetheless, a lot of businesses struggle with performance, which has caused some to fail entirely or to be unable to meet their goals and objectives. Effective leadership is therefore essential to every organization's development. A leader is someone who leads, mentors, inspires, and persuades others to achieve predetermined goals and objectives.

In the words of Abodunde, et al (2020), a leader is responsible in determining values, culture, and tolerance among employees. These leaders can be found at any level of an organization, not just in positions of authority. Leaders who have achieved success in organizations, most often, have something in common.

Performance of employee is and important aspect of organization. Employee performance is one aspect of that plays a significant role on the success of an organization. Leadership on the other hand, is perhaps the most investigated organizational variable that has a potential impact on employee performance (Kim, 2021).

Hersey and Blanchard (2021) define leadership as the process of influencing a group's or an individual's performance in order to attain a goal in a particular circumstance. Therefore, leadership in this study refers to the performance of the individual designated by the organization or owner to oversee all or a subset of the organization's activities. According to the school of thinking that shifted from "Trait theories" to transformational leadership theories, employee performance and leadership style are strongly correlated. Later theories start to take into account the role of followers and the contextual aspect of leadership, whereas early theories tend to concentrate on the traits and actions of effective leaders.

Statement of the Problem

Leadership is the art and craft of influencing the thinking and behaviour of audiences to achieve mutual goals, leadership is not about what leaders do, but the relationship between leaders and audiences (Bilola, 2023). Organization with poor or less skilled leaders will always perform below expectations, in turns out that the poor leaders may lack vision and adequate understanding of the role of a good and skilled leader.

Researcher around the world have debated the impact of leadership style on worker performance. However, one of the concerns that needs to be properly addressed in organizational management is the impact of leadership styles on staff performance manipulation. Leaders in inefficient organizations are typically very controlling. They are the only ones who want to make decision . Going by the array of the above problems associated with bad leadership style on organizational performance, there is therefore the need to examine the effects of the different leadership styles on employee performance, with a view to assessing the right style that is appropriate to reaping higher employee performance. It is stated that no leadership style has proven to be the best, the researcher adopted transformational leadership style and participative leadership style for this study. In line with this, the researcher seeks to examined, effect of leadership style on the employee performance of Federal College of Educational (FCE) Obudu, Cross River State as a study.

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of this study is to determine how leadership style affect employee performance in Federal College of Education (FCE), Obudu. Other specific objectives include following:

- i. To examine the effect of transformational leadership style on employee performance in (FCE), Obudu.
- ii. To assess the effect of participative leadership style on employee performance in (FCE), Obudu.

Research Questions

- i. To what extent does transformational leadership style on employee performance in (FCE), Obudu?
- ii. To what extent does participative leadership style on employee performance in (FCE), Obudu?

Statement of Hypotheses

For the course of this study, the following hypothesis has been formulated as a guide for this study.

H_0^1 : There is no significant relationship between transformational leadership style and employee performance in (FCE) Obudu.

H_0^2 : Participative leadership style has not significant effect on employee performance in (FEC), Obudu.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept of Leadership

According to Hazem et al. (2023), leadership is a means of setting goals, bringing people together, and inspiring and motivating them. Leadership is more about people than it is about tasks. Leaders often use a combination of these skills interest because they focus on things like finding solution (not problem), managing change, succeeding despite organizational structure, and inspiring employees to achieve their goals. Leadership has become the primary priority in today's corporate climate. Today's corporate environment has made leadership the central concern, the reason for this is that it is in charge of integrating and balancing material and human resources to generate the output or services that the body was designed to provide. The practice of inspiring others to reach their greatest potential in the pursuit of a shared, value-added vision with zeal and honesty is known as leadership. The relationship a leader has with each of their followers is a crucial component of the leadership process.

In the words of Eze (2019), leadership is a relation term that involves both the person being influenced and the one exerting influence. He asserted that this implies that a leader cannot exist without followers. Additionally, he stated that the qualities of the situation in which he is leading as well as the skills and traits of the group he is leading are factors that combine to create an effective leader. He went on to say that leadership, especially in the public sector, becomes the root cause of inefficiency and shoddiness, lack of seriousness, indiscipline, and rule enforcement. Thus, it is all about the continuous process of establishing and maintaining a connection between who aspire to lead and those who are willing to follow (Hersey and Blanchard 2020).

Transformational Leadership

The distinctiveness between transformational leadership has to do with their unique way of motivating others. In transformational leadership, their behavior takes into account their values and conviction, and they try to motivate their subordinates to perform more than required to promote the organizational goals (Bass, 2018). Transformational leadership is a process where leaders and subordinates hold each other to a higher level of morality and motivation (Burns, 2019). Many scholars have widely recognized transformational leadership as one of the important factors influencing innovation in an organization. According to Samad (2019), transformational leadership is vital because they integrate persistence, creative insight, and sensitivity to employees' input that prompt positive management changes. Transformational leadership, encourages employees' creativity by recognizing their individuality and encouraging more diverse perspectives and approaches. in the banking sector, Jalees (2017) discovered that helping employees to develop their skills helps in enhancing their creativity in thinking out new approaches to do things.

Transformational leaders instill trust, loyalty, admiration, and respect on their subordinates, which helps motivate them to give in their best in any given task and promote organizational

goals willingly (Karz, 2020). Their subordinates perceive transformational leaders as competent individuals with great character, determination, and high ethical behavior (Bass, 2018). Transformational leaders sacrifice self-gain for an overall gain of others, and most especially, a gain in the organization; they take into account the subordinates need over their own needs most of the time, and takes the subordinates input and suggestions seriously when making a decision (Limsila & Ogunlana, 2018).

Participative Leadership

Participative leadership is seen as making a decision jointly or demonstrating a shared influence in determining superior and subordinate through the hierarchy. As such, the focus of participatory management has become the sharing of power and decision-making allocation, (Osama, & Hamzah, 2022). Participative leadership is seen as a kind of leadership that embrace all member of an organization making clear the importance of the organizational goals as well as setting up strategies and procedures to achieve the goals. The participative leader possesses consultative behaviors, such as imploring subordinates for ideas prior to making an ultimate decision, although, they retain final decision authority. The participative leader shares duties with subordinates by encompassing them in the preparation, decision-making, and implementation phases (Oluwatoyin, & Nkechi, 2023). Mahnoor, (2024) identified this type of style as one that involves the leader including one or more employees in the decision making process (determining what to do and how to do it).

Theoretical Review

This research is anchored on behavioural theory

Behavioural Theory

Behavioural theory was first propounded by Kurt Lewin in 1940, the theory emerged as significant development in leadership and management studies in the Mid-20th century. It evolved as a reaction to the limitations of the trait theory. the theory proposes that effective leadership is based on observable behaviour that can be learned, practiced and improved over time. This brought about a shift from who leaders are to what they do. Behavioural theory asserts that leadership effectiveness depends primarily on the actions and behaviours of the leader rather than on innate traits or personality characteristics. It assumes that leadership skills can be taught, learned and developed through observation, experience, and training. This approach focuses on identifying and nurturing specific behaviours that produce desired outcomes in the workplace, such as motivating employees, fostering teamwork, and improving performance

Empirical Review

In 2024, Mahnor investigated participative leadership style on employee performance, the study considered employee leaning in institution when participative leadership style is practiced to check if the performance of the employee improves or not. The study adopted a quantitative approach data was collected through structured questionnaire. The findings indicated that participative leadership style has a positive and significant impact on employee performance

In a study by Sylvia, (2023) on the relationship between transformational leadership style and organizational performance in developing countries. The methodology of the study was aligned with that of Grant and Booth (2009), whereby secondary data is recognized as a sufficient for data collection. The findings indicated that transformational leadership study plays a significant role in shaping organizational performance. it was then concluded that, organizational should create an environment where leaders are able to motivate and encourage employee to exercise innovativeness and creativity through transformational leadership style.

Osama, & Hamzah, (2022) carried out a study on the effective of participative leadership style on employee performance. the study adopted a cross-sectional, where date was gathered from 347 participant from all managerial levels in the United Arab Emirate. The findings revealed the effectiveness of participative leadership style on employees performance.

Thamer (2021) examine the impact of participative leadership style on workers performance, using Saudi Arabia public sector as a survey. The researcher used a quantitative survey method. Ministry of foreign affairs was used as the population for the study.101 employees was used. Te result from the analysis revealed participative leadership style play a significant role on workers performance in the public sector of Saudi Arabi.

The impact of transformational leadership style was examine d by Hira in (2020). A cross-sectional survey was used to gather information from 308 in the telecom industry. Model 4 process of Hayes was utilized to investigate the hypotheses. The outcome demonstrated a strong and favourable correlation between transformative leadership and employee performance. The researcher noted that while transformational leadership can motivate workers to perform better, organizational leaders can possess transformational qualities by been well informed about their workforce.

METHODOLOGY

For the purpose of the study and to enable the researcher examine the effect of leadership style on employee performance in Federal College of Education (FCE), Obudu. The researcher adopted a descriptive research design

Population of the Study

In this study, the population includes both academic staff and non-academic staff of FEC, Obudu, The population of the study is made up of 400 employees, in the following categories as shown in. Table 3.1

Table 3.1: Total Population Distribution of FCE Employees

Categorization of Employees	Number
Academic Staff	360
Senior Staff	740

Junior Staff	84
Total	1184

Source: Field Survey: Personnel Record (2025)

Sample size Determination

Sample size is a small group of subjects drawn from the interest of the researcher, to enable the researcher gather useful information. Sample enables the researcher to achieve the objectives with reduced resources. The researcher adopted Taro Yamane Sample size determination given as thus:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where;

N = population size

n = sample size

e =tolerable error term

1 is constant

$$n = \frac{1184}{1 + 1184 (0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{1184}{1 + 1184 (0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{1184}{1+ 2.96}$$

$$n = \frac{1184}{2.9}$$

n = 408

The sample size of the study is 408

Research Instrument

The researcher made use of questionnaires to collect data from the respondent. The questionnaires were designed with closed-ended questions. The study adopted the five point liker scale, SA= Strongly Agree, A = Agreed, U = Undecided, D = Disagree and SD = Strongly Disagree. This liker scale will give the respondents option to answer the questions

Data Analysis

The data collected from the respondents were checked for accuracy, edited and well coded before analyzing using Pearson moment correlation coefficient with the aid of statistical package for social science (SPSS) 27.0 to accomplish the research objectives the collected data was analyzed using descriptive statistics.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Data Presentation

The table below show the distribution of questionnaires to the respondents in their various department and numbers.

Table 2: Questionnaires administered to respondents

Category	Number of questionnaires distributed	Number of questionnaires returned	Percentage of questionnaires returned
Academic Staff	118	102	25
Senior Staff	241	169	41.8
Junior Staff	45	39	10
Total	404	310	76

Source: Researcher's Fieldwork, 2025

Table 4.1 showed the response rate from the questionnaire distributed. From the table, a total of 404 copies of questionnaires were distributed with academic staff getting 118, Senior staff 169, Junior staff 45. Out of the copies of questionnaires distributed, Academic staff correctly filled and returned 102 representing 25 per cent, Senior staff 169 representing 41.8 Per cent, Junior staff 39 representing 10 per cent, This data shows that 76 per cent of the copies of questionnaires distributed were correctly filled and returned.

Test of Hypotheses

Table 2: Multi Co-linearity Test

	Co-linearity statistics	
	Tolerance	Variance inflation factor (VIF)
(Constant)		
Transformational Leadership	.228	7.792
Participative Leadership	.201	4.979

Source: Researcher’s Computation from SPSS.27.0.

A condition of extremely high inter-correlation or inter-association between the independent variable is known as multi-co-linearity. We concluded that there was no multi-co-linearity problem in the data because the tolerances were larger than 0.2 and the VIFs were fewer than 10. As a result. We can proceed with the analysis without making any changes.

Table 3 Model Summary

<i>Model Summary^b</i>					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin Watson
1	.941 ^a	.885	.876	.503	1.724
a. Predictors: (Constant), Transformational Leadership, Participative Leadership b. Dependent variable: Employee performance					

Source: Researcher’s Computation from SPSS.27, 2024

A linear regression analysis conducted to ascertain the effect of leadership style on the performance of employee Table 4.3 shows that there is strong positive relationship between transformational leadership and employee performance (R- coefficient = .941). The R square, the coefficient of determination, showed that 88.5% of the variation in employee performance can be explained by leadership style with no autocorrelation as Durbin-Watson (1.724) was less than 2. With the linear regression model, the error of estimate is low, with a value of about .503

Table4 ANOVA

<i>ANOVA^a</i>						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	95.486	4	23.871	94.447	.000b
	Residual	12.385	49	.253		
	Total	107.870	53			

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance
b. Predictors: (Constant), Transformational Leadership Participative leadership

Source: Researcher’s Computation from SPSS.27, 2024

The F statistic table reveals the overall significance of the model, the probability value of 0.000 which is below the level of significance indicate that we reject null hypothesis and conclude that Leadership style has a significant effect on the employee performance.

Table 5 Regression Coefficients

<i>Coefficients^a</i>						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.068	.206		332	.000
	Transformational Leadership Style	.206	.130	.214	1.587	.001
	Participative Leadership Style	.354	.102	.376	3.483	.001

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

Source: Researcher’s Computation from SPSS.27, 2024

The coefficient table reveals the relationship between the variables which shows that the variables have a positive relationship with employee performance with 0.068 and 0.206. The table further reveals the significance of the explanatory variables which was however used to test the hypotheses of the study. However, the table reveals that leadership style is statistically significant with probability value of 0.000 also, transformational leadership and participative leadership were significant with probability values of 0.001,0.001, 0.002 and 0.000 respectively with employee performance at 5% level of significance.

4.3 Discussion of Findings

The following findings were discussed.

The first objective was to examine the effect of transformational leadership style on employee performance of federal college of Education (FCE), Obudu. The result of the hypothesis indicated that transformational leadership style have significant bearing on employee performance of (FCE), Obudu. The result of the findings is in line with findings of Sylvia, (2023) examined the relationship between transformational leadership style and organizational performance in developing countries. The findings indicated that transformational leadership study plays a significant role in shaping organizational performance. it was then concluded that, organizational should create an environment where leaders are able to motivate and encourage employee to exercise innovativeness and creativity through transformational leadership style.

The second objective was to determine the effect of participative leadership style on the employee performance of (FCE), Obudu the result from hypothesis two shows a significant positive relationship between participative leadership style and employee performance of (FCE), Obudu.

This finding was supported by findings of Mahnoor, (2024) who examined the impact of participative leadership style on employee's performance: The findings indicate that participative leadership style has a positive and significant impact on employee performance.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.2 Conclusion

This research work has proven that for any organization to have a well performed employee, appropriate leadership style must be adopted rightly. The study examined the effect of leadership style on employee performance of Federal College of education (FCE), Obudu. The study employ transformational leadership style and participative leadership style as the proxies for the independent variable Leadership style on the performance of employee of (FCE), Obudu The study concluded that, the importance of leadership style on the performance of employee is without doubt very eminent. The leadership style adopted by a leader has the ability to either spur performance or discourage higher performance. The study has shown that the leadership style considered affect employee performance positively. However, the leaders should know when to adopt these styles because if it is not properly and timely implemented, it may impact negatively on employee performance.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the findings from the study, it is necessary to offer the following recommendations.

1. Management should set up policy that will embrace transformational kind of leadership as the study has proven it to be very important in boosting the performance of the organization.
2. The study recommended that Leaders should create opportunities for employees to contribute ideas and opinions during planning and problem-solving processes. This enhances employees' sense of ownership, responsibility, and commitment, which in turn improves performance and job satisfaction.

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